

8T –Momenta and Wavelength

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting in which 8T is built upon, i.e. Lorentz manifold and calculus of variation, author will build an analog for the relationship which defined the physics of the 20-th century. The relation between momenta and wavelength. In particular author will argue that the more curved a net variation is, i.e. a Boson, the faster it gets flatten, which means diverging across space, which means higher momenta. The author presents the known relation using recent advancement in theoretical and conceptual physics.

Introduction

The main equation of the 8T associate energy to a degree of curvature. that is given by the main equation which describe the process of acceleration from extremum curvature on the manifold.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

The Bosons in the 8T were proven net curvature of discrete amount on the matrix tensor, given by the primordial coupling constants series. The primordial series has two main forms, net curvature formation and the spin formation.

$$\left(2e^- * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + e^-_{\mu} \right) + \gamma_{\mu} = 30:128:850:9254 \dots \quad (2)$$

The subscript stands for a five vector that is given by:

$$\mu = (\nabla^2, t_n, s_n)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t_n^2} N_V = \nabla^2 N_V \quad (2.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial t_n^2} = \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial z^2}$$

In the recent past 8T has defined "Energy" or the "Hamiltonian" of the system as the arrow:

$$\varphi: g \rightarrow E$$

$$E = \hat{H}$$

Given that introduction, it is possible to construct an analog for the relation that defined physics of the past century, the relation between momenta and wavelength. That can be done in several ways. Since each photon is a net curvature diverging unbound, and by the arrow above, that curvature is accounting for a certain energy, the more curved the element the more energy it contains. That is how one presented the EMT symmetry of equation (2). The setting of the theory is stationary manifold in which curvature is "not allowed", i.e. the manifold aspires to reach the lowest state of energy, or flatness, because of being of a packet of manifolds which flatten each other via areas of extremum curvatures. Therefore, for that we have momenta, which must be in inverse relation to the wavelength. The shorter the wavelength, the higher the diverging rate of the curvature across the matrix, due to the stationarity condition. The longer the diverging process, the amount of energy is devised across larger areas so that the manifold can "get rid" of those elements which violate the stationarity condition first. What is new here is not the relation of the two terms, but rather the reasoning and the nature of photons when considered in a variational curvature framework. Then we can extrapolate the usual relation, curvature is inversely proportional to wavelength, and wavelength is inversely proportional to momenta. Which indicating that the momenta is directly proportional to curvature/energy. The shorter wavelength the higher the energy, the higher the momenta, and the faster the wave or ripple or curvature travels or diverge all across, so as a result this is the 8T explanation to the fact that the earthly sky are blue.

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

M. Ohad B Theory